

Synthesis of Highly Oriented Graphite Films with a Low Wrinkle Density and Near-Millimeter Scale Lateral Grains

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Abstract

Principal defects found in graphite films include grain boundaries and wrinkles. These defects are well known to have detrimental effects on properties such as thermal and electrical conductivities as well as mechanical properties. With a two-fold objective of synthesizing graphite films with large single crystal grains and no wrinkles, we have developed a relatively low temperature ($< 1150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) process that involves the precipitation of graphite films from nickel-carbon solid solutions followed by in-situ etching of the nickel foil substrates with anhydrous chlorine gas to obtain *near wrinkle free* continuous graphite films. The size (L_a) distribution of lateral grains (or single crystal regions) in these highly oriented graphite films has been found to be asymmetric with the largest grains about 0.9 mm in diameter, as determined by electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD). Thus, the growth of large area graphite films with grains much larger than those reported for highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG, $\sim 20\text{--}30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$), and with a low density of wrinkles, as in the case of HOPG, but prepared at much lower temperatures, is reported here.

Introduction

Methods such as the molten flux route ($> 1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)¹⁻⁵ or the metal-carbon solid solution route⁶⁻¹⁷ have been explored to synthesize graphite crystals in the bulk form or as thin films. However, the graphite films generated are often heavily wrinkled, a defect that, along with grain boundaries, dislocations, and vacancies, is largely detrimental to their properties, including thermal and electrical conductivities and mechanical properties. Moreover, although some published studies provide selected area diffraction patterns from transmission electron microscope (TEM) analysis, the analyses are limited to regions $\lesssim 1\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$, and, none of these papers report the grain sizes of these graphite materials. Another route to synthesizing graphite involves the thermal cracking of hydrocarbons at very high temperatures ($> 2000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) with applied pressure. This process tends to yield non-wrinkled “highly oriented pyrolytic graphite” (HOPG) as products, but the grain sizes are typically limited to $\sim 20\text{--}30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (for grade A HOPG).¹⁸ Another variant of the molten flux method to prepare graphite is the kish-method where graphite flakes are obtained by the precipitation of C from molten steel. Although these flakes may contain single crystals up to $\sim 1\text{ mm}$ in size, they contain iron impurities that must be removed by additional purification.⁴

In this work, we have explored the synthesis of graphite films with minimal wrinkles and large grains by precipitation from Ni-C solid solutions in the temperature range of $1000\text{--}1150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Ni-C solid solution may be considered a model system to study and control the precipitation of graphite films for the following reasons: (1) the Ni{111} surface is lattice matched to the graphene layers, (2) Ni does not undergo additional reactions (such as, phase changes or carbide formation) at our temperatures of interest that could otherwise complicate the process, and (3) C dissolution and segregation and precipitation from Ni have been previously studied in detail by *in-situ* techniques such as LEED and Auger electron spectroscopy by several surface science groups.¹⁹⁻²³ Methane was selected as the C precursor of choice as it is a thermally stable hydrocarbon that can only be catalytically decomposed in

H₂ rich environments at temperatures < 1200 °C: this approach minimizes “soot” or amorphous carbon formation from thermally mediated reactions.

Our typical graphite growth process involved (1) exposure of the Ni foils to CH₄ gas at T_{dissolution} to form the Ni-C solutions followed by (2) precipitation of the graphite films at a lower T_{precipitation} under vacuum and (3) a final cooling step to room temperature RT (Process A, **Figure 1**). Films generated using this process were heavily wrinkled (or buckled) where wrinkles are defined as vertical deviations from a flat surface (**Figure S2**). Such films are referred to as *Type A* films in this manuscript (**Figures 2, S3, S4**). The major cause of the formation of wrinkles in thin films synthesized at high temperatures (> 800 °C) is the thermal stress generated due to the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE's) between the thin film and the growth substrate (other factors such as intrinsic stresses generated during growth and extrinsic stresses due to external factors may also cause wrinkling). For example, when cooled from a growth temperature of 1000 °C to RT, the lattice parameter ‘a’ of face centered cubic (FCC) Ni changes from 3.58 Å to 3.52 Å (i.e. ~1.7% contraction)²⁴ while for graphite, the change in the in-plane lattice constant is negligible (**Figure S5**).^{25, 26} This unequal contraction introduces biaxial compressive stresses in the film that are released by forming a network of delamination buckles in the film.

Wrinkling may distort the local crystal symmetry and thus introduce bond strain and crystallographic defects in the graphite film. On a more severe level, wrinkling may even lead to bond breakage in graphite films. Wrinkling has been observed to degrade several material properties in graphene²⁷⁻²⁹ or to enhance its chemical reactivity.^{30, 31} Strategies to prevent wrinkling in single layer graphene include growth on copper substrates with a specific crystallographic orientation (Cu(111)),^{32, 33} switching to lower CTE substrates like metallic platinum³⁴ or non-metallic germanium,³⁵ or, growth at lower temperatures (Cu/Ni(111) at 750 °C).³⁶ However, to the best of our knowledge, no attempts on eliminating wrinkling in graphite or multi-layer graphene films have been reported in the literature.

Results and Discussion

Our approach for preventing wrinkle formation in graphite films has been to remove *physical contact* between the Ni foil and the graphite films immediately after growth at 1000 °C and then cool the resulting free-standing graphite films to RT. This essentially involved chemically etching the Ni foil(s) at $T_{\text{precipitation}}$ or 1000 °C. An ideal reagent for this purpose should have the following characteristics: (1) be stable at 1000 °C, (2) have sufficient vapor pressure for easy introduction into a reactor under dynamic gas flow conditions, (3) selectively react with the Ni foil(s), (4) form reaction products with sufficient vapor pressures that can be removed without contaminating the graphite films, (5) not introduce defects into the graphite films, and finally, (6) not interfere with the graphitization process of the dissolved C in the Ni foil(s).

Commercial etchants and aqueous solutions of non-oxidizing and oxidizing acids, such as HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄ or H₃PO₄, that are commonly used for etching Ni at temperatures < 200 °C cannot be used for high temperature etching inside a reactor. Oxidizing reagents such as supercritical water or oxygen gas will also completely or partially oxidize the graphite film (and possibly also generate CH₄, CO, or CO₂) while converting the Ni foil to nickel oxide powder. Similarly, sulfur-containing etchants such as H₂S acid vapor are known to produce stable S-doped graphene at temperatures above ~600 °C.³⁷ Again, anhydrous HCl or other non-oxidizing acid vapors cannot be used because HCl will produce H₂ gas, both by thermal dissociation (~0.73% at 1000 °C),³⁸ and reaction with Ni and this H₂ may etch the graphene layers. Moreover, as the remaining dissolved C in the Ni foil graphitizes as the foil is etched (discussed in detail later), the presence of H₂ may complicate this process by creating vacancies or sp³ carbon. Indeed, H₂-Cl₂ mixtures have been used to form nano-diamond particles or sp³ carbons that are not wanted in our process.^{39, 40}

It has been shown that the carbon-halogen bonds in halo-graphenes⁴¹ and graphite fluoride⁴² are unstable at temperatures above 400–700 °C. For example, the C-Cl bond is not stable at high temperatures and pristine graphene can be recovered from chlorinated graphene by heating to temperatures > 500 °C.^{43, 44} Indeed, one method of purifying natural and kish graphites industrially is by exposing them to anhydrous Cl₂ gas at high temperatures.⁴ Moreover, the synthesis of carbide derived carbons (CDCs) has been explored by reacting carbides MC_x (M = Si, Al, Ti, Zr, V, Nb, Ta etc.) with Cl₂-Ar under dynamic flow and at ambient pressure at ~900–1000 °C to form graphitic C and MCl_x.^{45, 46} The other halogens react similarly with MC_x and are all potentially suitable agents for etching Ni at high temperatures without damaging the graphite film.^{46, 47} Because anhydrous Cl₂ gas has a higher reactivity than Br₂ and I₂, and because they are respectively a liquid and a solid that would require additional optimization of appropriate bubbler type set-ups, we selected Cl₂ for the etching process. Fluorine was not selected because of its severe safety hazards.

In order to remove wrinkles, after the graphite films had been formed at 1000 °C ($T_{\text{precipitation}}$), anhydrous Cl₂ gas was introduced for ~3 h to etch away the Ni foil sandwiched between the two graphite films that had grown on its two sides (Process B, **Figure 1**). The temperature for graphite growth and subsequent Ni etching was selected to be 1000 °C to ensure that the NiCl₂ produced did not contaminate the graphite films because NiCl₂ has a high enough vapor pressure to be removed from the reaction zone with a dynamic vacuum.

It is important to note that for the graphite growth runs in which the Ni was etched (process B), the Ni foils were placed in boats with covers to prevent the resulting free-standing graphite films from flying away under this dynamic vacuum (**Figure S6**). As the Ni etching progressed, orange anhydrous NiCl₂ powder was deposited on the cooler surfaces of the reactor (**Figure S7**). When the graphite growth and Ni etching were finished, the Cl₂ gas was turned off and the films were cooled to RT after a 5 min wait at 1000 °C. This wait time was necessary to pump out all the Cl₂ gas before cooling in order to

eliminate any possible chance of C-Cl bond formation at lower temperatures ($< 500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). At this point, these graphite films no longer had a Ni substrate in physical contact and hence, did not experience the $\sim 1.7\%$ biaxial compressive stress they otherwise would have had. Once at RT, the films were recovered from the furnace and floated in ethanol or acetone. However, the two graphite films that had grown on the two sides of the Ni foil had collapsed onto each other (with a $\sim 80\text{--}100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ gap) after the Ni etching process. The films were then separated by gentle mechanical agitation with liquid N_2 (see SI for details) and tested for the presence of any metallic Ni(0) residue by bringing a magnet close to them. If the films were not attracted to the magnet, they were tentatively considered free of Ni(0) (**Figure S8**). The residual Ni concentration was later measured on select films by inductively coupled plasma- optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). The results given in **Table S2** show that the Ni content was quite small, $\sim 0\text{--}1\%$. The films were then transferred onto silicon wafers and air dried for further characterization. These films are referred to as *Type B films* in this manuscript.

The surfaces of the Type B graphite films were examined by optical microscopy (**Figure S9**) and SEM (**Figures 2, S10**) and showed a huge reduction in the total number of wrinkles. The films had lost their corrugated appearance and the larger wrinkles were completely absent. The few remaining wrinkles were possibly caused by mechanical stresses during handling of these free-standing sub-micrometer thick films. AFM imaging of the graphite surfaces showed that such wrinkles were $\sim 5\text{--}20\text{ nm}$ high and $\sim 0.1\text{--}0.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ wide. AFM imaging also showed that the films were “wavy” as might be expected from such free-standing films. Unsurprisingly, the film had occasional tears or holes, that were most likely a result of mechanical damage during the separation of the two films (**Figures 2, S11**).

The etching rate of Ni with Cl_2 was observed to be important for two main reasons. First, etching conditions that were “too harsh” mechanically damaged the films, forming, for example, torn and crumpled films when the Cl_2 flow rate or the reactor pressure were too high (**Figure S12**). Second, at $1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the Ni foil not only has graphite films on both surfaces but also about 1.3 atomic% C in the

bulk (**Figure 1**). This dissolved C graphitizes during the Ni etching step (neither the dissolved C nor the precipitated graphite are etched by Cl_2 at this temperature, as explained earlier). This suggests that the Ni etching rate may be an important parameter to consider to better control the C precipitation during Ni removal and the final structure of the graphite films. Hence, in order to form large graphite grains, the etching must be carried out at an optimized rate so that these C atoms are added to existing grains instead of randomly nucleating smaller new ones. Although we were able to optimize the etching rates so that minimally damaged films with large grains were produced, we were not able to independently evaluate the effects of rapid etching on the grain size, because this forms crumpled graphite films that could not be characterized by the diffraction techniques to be discussed later.

Graphite growth in process B thus occurs in two stages: (1) by non-isothermal precipitation as a result of a reduction in temperature from $T_{\text{dissolution}}$ to $T_{\text{precipitation}}$ (step 3, **Figure 1**), and, (2) by isothermal precipitation at $T_{\text{precipitation}}$ as the amount of Ni is reduced by chemical etching (thus continuously saturating the Ni with C; step 4, **Figure 1**). No obvious difference in quality was observed between graphite precipitated in steps 3 and 4 (see SI for details). As a consequence of this Ni etching step, Type B films were found to be much thicker than films grown without Ni etching, as performed for Type A films. Thus, Type B films have an average thickness of ~750–800 nm while Type A films have an average thickness of ~250 nm (**Figure S13**), values that approximately match the predicted thickness from C solubilities (Predicted: Type B, 805 nm; Type A, 265 nm; **Table S1**).

Initial characterization of the chemical nature of the as-synthesized films included electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis, and, Raman spectroscopy. EELS and XPS analyses showed that the film contained only sp^2 carbon and that no additional functionalization was present (**Figures S14, S32**). Raman mapping was performed on several samples to get information on film quality from the $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio and ranged from ~0.04–0.09 (**Figure S15, Table S3-i**) indicating that they were high quality with mostly sp^2 -bonded C atoms.

In order to determine the stacking order of the graphene layers, Raman mapping of the 2D peak was performed and the stacking order evaluated based on the method of Cancado et. al. (see Supporting Information (SI) for details).⁴⁸ For a Grade A HOPG sample with almost complete AB stacking, the metric obtained by this method was ~ 1.0 , whereas for these films (both Type A and Type B) it varied from ~ 0.84 – 1.0 (**Table S3-ii**). However, our films did show regions where the AB stacking order is obviously broken (**Figure S17**), but at this time, we are not certain what causes such disorder and hypothesize that such regions may be due to defects such as stacking faults or grain boundaries. These Raman results are consistent with the XRD data (discussed later) from which an ‘average’ d_{0002} spacing of 3.35 \AA was obtained for all samples, which also implies that the layers are mostly AB stacked.

The crystal dimensions in both the “a” (L_a or lateral dimensions) and the “c” directions (L_c) must be determined to define the size of a single crystal or grain in our films and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) has been used to determine the orientation and lateral grain size of the films. EBSD is a common technique for the determination of orientation and grain size in metallic and ceramic samples that utilizes Kikuchi patterns produced by backscattering of diffusely scattered electrons inside the sample for phase identification and determination of crystal orientation. EBSD analysis has been used for characterizing graphitic regions in iron^{49,50} and have been reported for graphite samples in two conference proceedings.^{51,52} To the best of our knowledge, there has been no earlier work on the use of EBSD to obtain a detailed and rigorous evaluation of grain orientation and size in graphite.

In order to verify that EBSD can be used to determine graphite grain orientation and size, EBSD was first performed on flakes of natural graphite transferred to silicon wafers. In EBSD, the software utilizes a user-defined sample co-ordinate system and phase to match the Kikuchi bands of the sample to reference patterns and determine crystal orientation.⁵³ Thus, one relatively stringent requirement is that the sample surface must be completely flat and perpendicular to the normal direction (ND) of the sample co-ordinate system at all points. Hence, all samples were pressed with a roller a few times

before measurement, which may have introduced additional wrinkles. Because graphite is a soft and layered material, no other chemo-mechanical polishing that is common for the preparation for metallic and ceramic samples for such studies was performed as it could have severely damaged the surface.

Orientation mapping involves the determination of crystal orientation (or index) of all pixels in a scan and then delineating grain boundaries based on the mis-orientation between these pixels. Hence, the first step after collecting the scan from a natural graphite flake was to evaluate the quality of the Kikuchi patterns obtained through an image quality (IQ) map (**Figure S18-i**) followed by the evaluation of the confidence index (CI) map that shows the CI values associated with each pixel. CI values represent the acceptability of the indexing results and range from 0–1 (**Figure S18-ii**). Only orientations with CI values > 0.1 were considered for subsequent analysis after processing (**Figure S18-iii**). Finally, the indexing success rate (ISR) was determined where ISR is simply the ratio of the points with CI values > 0.1 to the total number of scanned points. As shown in **Figure S18**, there is good correlation between the IQ and CI maps and the ISR is $\sim 99.6\%$, indicating that this is a good scan. Details of this process have been provided in the SI.

EBSD data may be represented by pole figures (PFs), inverse pole figures (IPFs), IPF maps and kernel average mis-orientation (KAM) maps. PFs plot specified crystal directions or poles of the different unit cells of the grains in the sample with respect to the sample co-ordinate system. On the other hand, IPFs plot a sample direction (such as the ND) with respect to specific crystal directions of the differently oriented unit cells in the sample. Thus, two key pieces of information are obtained simultaneously: the number or set of points reflects the number of grains in the sample whereas their locations indicate the location of specific crystal directions of the different grains (i.e., single crystal regions) with respect to the sample co-ordinate system. In both the PFs and IPFs the points have been weighted by the associated grain sizes for easy identification of a particularly large grain and multiple smaller grains, as is often the case. **Figure S19-I-i** plots the PFs for the $\langle 0001 \rangle$ and the $\langle 10\bar{1}1 \rangle$

crystal directions of the different grains in the scan for natural graphite. It contains two large points (for the (0001) PF) or sets of points (for the $(10\bar{1}1)$ PF) and several tiny (or sets of tiny) points, which implies that the scanned region contains two large grains. The IPF for the natural graphite scan (**Figure S19-I-ii**) plots the sample ND with respect to the crystal directions of the different grains. It contains points close to the $\langle 0001 \rangle$ direction implying that the $\langle 0001 \rangle$ directions of the different grains are essentially parallel to the sample ND. In other words, the $\{0001\}$ planes of all grains in the film are parallel to the sample surface. The IPF also shows two coincident large points, implying that two large grains are present. Finally, the IPF map is color coded to represent the orientation of the ND of each pixel in the scan, which for this scan is parallel to the $\langle 0001 \rangle$ directions of all associated grains (**Figure S19-III**). The last step of an EBSD scan involves delineating the grain boundaries and calculating the grain size (see SI). The grain diameters for regions 1 and 2 have been calculated from their areas to be $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 450 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. **Figure S19-IV** shows the KAM map from the natural graphite scan comparing mis-orientation between neighboring pixels; mis-orientation between 1st nearest neighbors is generally $< 2^\circ$.

Several Type B films have been analyzed by EBSD. However, perhaps because of an uneven surface topography the ISR values were somewhat lower. Smaller scan areas ($\leq 125 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$) tended to have larger ISR values ($\sim 99\%$) but the grain sizes were artificially limited by the areas scanned (**Figures 3, S20-S21** and **Table S4**). To determine the ‘true’ grain sizes, EBSD scans over an area of about $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^2$ were performed. **Figure 4** shows the IPF and PF plots for two Type B films with $\{0001\}$ orientation and the largest grains about 0.9 mm in diameter. The (0001) PFs for both films show a single large point and the $(10\bar{1}1)$ PFs show one set of large points, confirming that these regions are single crystals. The yellow regions in the IPF map and the circled points in the PFs and the IPFs are from the exposed silicon wafer where the films have holes or tears (**Figure S27**). A large area scan from a Type A wrinkled film is shown in **Figure S23** and shows that the largest grain diameter is about

0.8 mm. KAM maps and details of all large area scans have been provided in **Figure S22** and **Table S5**.

A probable reason for lower ISRs can be obtained by comparing the maps in **Figure S24**, where the SEM image (i), the ‘raw’ IQ map (ii) and the IQ (iii) and the CI (iv) maps from post-processing are shown. From these figures, it is obvious that non-flat regions have lower IQ values that result in low CI values and poor indexing. In this example, the non-flat regions are the ones where the film has torn material deposited on top of it which perhaps obscures Kikuchi patterns from the film lying beneath it. However, even without material deposited on top and a sharp Kikuchi pattern, local surface curvature (i.e., any deviation from the user defined sample co-ordinate system), may result in a failure by the software to index the pixel with an acceptable CI value and lead to an overall lower ISR for the scan.

Figure 5 shows a comparison between similar area scans from a Type B film, a natural graphite flake and commercial grade A HOPG. It is concluded from the unique grain color maps that grain sizes in grade A HOPG are much smaller (6–26 μm) than in the natural or Type B graphite samples. Again, the quasi ring-like appearance of the $(10\bar{1}1)$ PF of grade A HOPG versus the single set of large points for natural graphite or the Type B graphite film clearly demonstrates that the grains in HOPG are much smaller.

XRD experiments that involved coupled ω - 2θ scans with a 0-D detector were performed to probe the crystal structure in the “c” direction and showed that the films have a preferred orientation because only the $\{0002\}$ family of peaks was detected. The d_{0002} values calculated from these scans were all clustered around 3.354 Å (**Table S7-i**) which implies that the films are, on average, AB stacked (a higher d_{0002} value would imply turbostratic stacking).⁵⁴ This result does not contradict the Raman spectroscopic analysis discussed earlier showing occasional deviations from AB stacking. This is because Raman spectroscopy has a much higher resolution (spot size of beam ~ 700 – 800 nm at 100x

magnification; information depth ~30 nm) whereas XRD provides an average value for the entire film (spot size of beam ~1 mm; information depth ~entire film).

Mosaic spread is a parameter that is commonly used for HOPG samples to determine crystallite (or single crystal) alignment in the 'c' direction and a lower value of this metric signifies greater crystallite alignment (see SI for details). The mosaic spread values obtained were in the range ~0.1–0.2° for Type B films and ~0.5° for Type A films. This indicates crystallite alignment in Type B films is at least as good as in Grade A HOPG, keeping in mind that these films were not perfectly flat which may artificially increase the mosaic spread value.

High resolution-TEM (HR-TEM) was also used to study and compare Type A and Type B graphite films (**Figure 6**). Electron transparent Type A films imaged in the top-down mode (plan view TEM) showed a heavily wrinkled appearance with 3–4 wrinkles often emerging from common junction points. High magnification images of these junction regions revealed 'gaps' where the graphene layers had physically separated, possibly due to shear stress. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) of such junctions was then done to explore whether wrinkling had locally modified the orientation. SAED showed no change in orientation although additional diffraction spots were present, possibly from the folded over part in the wrinkle. On the other hand, cross-section TEM imaging performed on thicker and thinner Type A films revealed two types of large angular bends ($> 100^\circ$) in the {0002} lattice fringes of the graphene layers. These include ~130–160° conformal bends adjacent to the Ni substrate and ~130–150° nano-buckles within the graphene layers of the film. Nano-buckles may show variations in the d_{0002} lattice fringe spacing and may have adjacent physical gaps. Both nano-buckles and conformal bends may have neighboring regions of lower crystallinity. Details of the TEM characterization of Type A wrinkled films and the possible implication of buckling of the graphene layers on the growth process and film properties will be reported elsewhere.

For Type B films, plan-view HR-TEM on a film thinned to electron transparency by mechanical exfoliation showed the region to be a single crystal with AB stacking. **Figures 6-(viii)** and **(ix)** were obtained from the cross-section of a Type B film and respectively show the diffraction pattern and a high-resolution image, proving that it is a highly crystalline material. Again, the sharpness of the diffraction spots indicates that this is a single crystal region.

In order to further understand the role of the Ni substrate on graphite grain size, attempts were made to correlate the grain structure of the Ni substrate to that of the graphite film. It was found that considerable grain growth had occurred in the Ni foil after the H₂ pre-treatment step (step 1, **Figure 1**), and that the foil contained grains of different orientations that could be as large as ~850 μm (**Figure S29**). The fact that the largest graphite grains were also ~800–900 μm in size suggests that a relationship may exist between the grain sizes of the graphite film and the Ni substrate. Again, the graphite grains were always found to have the {0001} orientation. Thus, the graphene layers of the films grow parallel to the Ni substrate irrespective of the orientation of the Ni grains. This has been previously observed by Johansson et. al. while exploring the orientations of their graphite films and the underlying polycrystalline Ni substrate by electron diffraction in the TEM.⁵⁵ Additional details on the role of the substrate on graphite film growth is currently in progress and will be reported elsewhere.

One of the major improvements expected from the removal of wrinkles in graphite films is a significant increase in their Young's modulus and stiffness. Hence, removing wrinkles from an area fraction = 0.1, from films that have (wrinkle amplitude/film thickness) ratios ranging from 1–10, would increase their respective Young's modulus by a factor 0.6–60.⁵⁶ However, the removal of wrinkles is not expected to significantly influence the film strength, and, potential applications for wrinkle-free graphite films are where “high modulus carbon films” are required (similar to high modulus carbon fibers that are obtained by the removal of misalignment between the constituent crystalline carbon ribbons).

On the other hand, removal of grain boundaries is expected to increase film strength and stiffness.^{57, 58} An increase in grain size has been observed in silico as capable of increasing the fracture strength of polycrystalline graphene, following an inverse Hall-Petch like relation and demonstrating that the grain boundary junctions are the weakest links. From this result, ~2 times increase in strength may be expected with an increase in grain size d in a graphite film of a size L , when the L/d ratio changes from 10000 to 10. Accordingly, the potential applications for both wrinkle and grain boundary free graphite films are where “high modulus and high strength carbon films” are required. A detailed discussion can be found in the SI.

Conclusions

We have shown that we can grow graphite films with few wrinkles by growing them on Ni foils at high temperatures and then removing the Ni substrates by chemical etching to eliminate issues caused by CTE differences between the films and the foils. Moreover, by optimizing the process parameters, we have grown continuous graphite films with near-millimeter scale lateral grains. We believe that this is the first report of an attempt to reduce wrinkling in thin films of a layered material, with single layer graphene being a notable exception. This is also the first rigorous attempt to unambiguously determine grain sizes in graphite by EBSD, which has been used extensively for this purpose. Initial calculations on mechanical properties predict a significant improvement in axial stiffness and strength in these films attributed to a reduction in the number of wrinkles and an increase in grain size.

However, intrinsic stresses from the growth process and external stresses generated after the growth process that may cause other defects including fine wrinkles have not been eliminated or studied. The current technical limitations of the overall process include the formation of holes or tears in the films and the inability to obtain pristine thin films of graphite or multi-layer graphene, both due to the difficulty of handling such free-standing films in the reactor without mechanical damage. Such

limitations may be removed with appropriate equipment and experimental design modifications, such as by using more suitable sample holders. In the future, we hope to see such films generated so that the expected property improvements discussed above can be studied and evaluated.

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Figures

Figure 1. Details of the production of **Type A** and **B** films: (i) overall process, (ii) schematic of the process inside the reactor, and, (iii) plots of variation in C solubility with temperature in polycrystalline Ni showing the amounts of C precipitated as graphite during steps **3** (due to a reduction in temperature), and, **4** (due to Ni etching) of the process (ST = step).

Figure 2. SEM and AFM images of graphite films. **Type A** films: (i) SEM image, and, (ii)-(iv) AFM images; **Type B** films: (v)-(vi) SEM images, and, (vii)-(xii) AFM images. All AFM images show $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ scan areas. Numbers across the wrinkles denote their heights in nanometers.

Figure 3. EBSD scans of **Type B** graphite films. (I) A high resolution scan with a step size of 250 nm, and, (II) A scan where the grain size is limited by the scan size: (i) IPF map of the sample ND (Scale bars: 5 μm (I), 50 μm(II)); (ii) IPF of the sample ND; (iii) left: (0001) PF, and, right: (1010) PF. Grain boundaries are represented in white and black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included in the IPF maps. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. ND refers to the normal or (001) direction of the sample co-ordinate system.

Figure 4. Large area EBSD scans of two **Type B** graphite films (I) and (II): (i) IPF map for the sample ND; (ii) IPF map for the sample ND with the largest grain highlighted in grey (Scale bars: (I) 600 μm ; (II) 500 μm); (iii) left: (0001) PF, and, right: (10 $\bar{1}$ 0) PF; (iv) IPF of the sample ND; (v) grain size chart with the largest grain highlighted in grey. Grain boundaries are represented in white and black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included in the IPF maps. Yellow regions in the IPF maps or the points circled in yellow on the IPFs and PFs are from the bare silicon wafer. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. ND refers to the normal or (001) direction of the sample co-ordinate system.

Figure 5. Comparison of similar sized EBSD scans ($\sim 125 \times 220 \mu\text{m}^2$): (I) Type B graphite film, (II) Natural graphite flake, (III) Grade A HOPG (Optigraph); (i) the IPF map for the normal direction of the sample co-ordinate system; (ii) the unique grain color map; (iii) left: (0001) PF, and, right: (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) PF for the respective scans. Scale bars for (i), and (ii): 50 μm . Grain boundaries are represented in white (IPF map) or grey (unique grain color map) and black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included. The points in the PFs have been weighted by grain size.

Figure 6. HR-TEM images and selected area diffraction (SAED) patterns of graphite films. **Type A** films: (i) a wrinkle junction; (ii) SAED patterns from a region containing a wrinkle junction (P: junction point) where spots adjacent to the stars are examples of select ‘additional’ spots in the patterns from wrinkles W1, W2 and P; R: region; (iii) defect-free crystal lattice; (iv) (1) lower and (2) higher magnification images of a region containing a conformal bend, and, diffraction patterns (right) from selected regions showing variation in crystallinity; (v) (1) lower and (2) higher magnification images of

a region containing a nano-buckle with the spacing of the d_{0002} lattice fringes in regions 1-3 tabulated below. **Type B** films: (vi) image, and, (vii) SAED pattern from a film thinned to electron transparency; (viii) SAED pattern, and, (ix) cross-section image of a typical ~ 800 nm film.

TOC Figure

